

Impact of Social Media on the Teacher-Taught Relationships

Dr. Sai Aanchal

Assistant Professor, Department of Sociology,
Sri Guru Gobind Singh College – Sector 26 (Affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh)
Chandigarh, India

Abstract:- In the present study, an attempt has been made to study the teachers' social media use and the purpose of using social media, time spent and content shared by the teachers on social media, and how the social media usage by the teachers and their students affected their teacher-taught relationships.

Keywords:- social media usage; social media impact; social media for teaching.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is important to understand that apart from the parents and peers, teachers also play a pertinent role in the lives of the adolescents. The study on the impact of social media is incomplete without examining the impact of social media usage on the teacher-taught relationship. Several studies confirmed that there was a positive impact of social media on the teacher-taught relationships when the teachers used social media for online teaching (Casey & Evans, 2011; Junco, Heiberger, & Loken, 2011; Sherer & Shea, 2011; Fewkes & McCabe, 2012; Domizi, 2013; June, Yaacob, & Kheng, 2014; Graham, 2014).

Churcher, Downs, and Tewksbury (2014: 43) have found in their study that Facebook usage enabled teachers to go beyond the traditional teacher-student relationship, which was earlier limited to their classrooms. The teachers used Facebook pages to assign tasks like subject assignments, pose questions, and share spellbinding facts about a topic they taught to their students. The students who were hesitant to open up in front of their teachers were more confident on Facebook. Online engagement of the students on academic posts via Facebook also helped them in improving their grades. Similar findings were reported by Krutka and Milton (2013).

June, Yaacob, and Kheng (2014) found that YouTube videos enhanced learning ability and stimulated students' critical thinking skills. Videos helped students visualize the content by relating it to practical problems and made it easy to understand lesson plans and lectures. Students also developed self-confidence during classroom discussions, and they were able to recall things in a better way, apply the acquired knowledge for problem-solving and generate better ideas.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Area of Study

The study was conducted in the city of Chandigarh because the city has a variety of schools having students who themselves, as well as their parents and teachers used social media.

B. Sampling Frame and Sample

For drawing the sample, the following three schools were purposively selected on the criterion of co-educational institutions and social media usage among students and teachers:

1. Delhi Public School (DPS), Sector - 40 C, Chandigarh
2. Guru Nanak Public School (GNPS), Sector - 36 D, Chandigarh
3. Shivalik Public School (SPS), Sector - 41 B, Chandigarh

30 teachers in the three schools who were teaching the students studying in Classes IX and XI, were personally interviewed.

C. Techniques of Data Collection

A semi-structured interview schedule was constructed for interviewing the teachers. The information retrieved have been incorporated in the form of simple frequency tables which were made with the help of SPSS. Inferences drawn from the data analysis have been discussed.

D. Objectives of the Study

The study focused upon the following objectives:

1. Studying the time spent on social media used by teachers, along with the purpose/s of social media usage;
2. Examining the manner in which the use of social media by students and teachers affects the teacher-taught relationship.

III. SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE BY THE TEACHERS

A. Time spent on social media by the teachers

According to a report based on a survey of 2.78 lakh respondents from 45 countries, Indian users spent approximately 2.4 hours on social networking and messaging applications like WhatsApp, and Facebook in 2019 (Mander, Kavanagh, & Buckle, 2019). The previous studies have indicated that a greater Internet and social media usage resulted in less time left for socializing with friends, family,

and waning interest in traditional media like newspapers (Nie & Erbring, 2002; Lee, 2009).

Thus, it was imperative to understand the time spent by the teachers on the social media. To understand the extent of social media usage, the teachers were asked about the time which they spent on social media. This was important to understand if the teachers used social media within a limit or in excess. Table 1. shows their responses:

Time Spent on Social Media	Schools			Total
	GNPS	DPS	SPS	
Less than 2 hours	4	3	3	10 (33.3%)
2-3 hours	6	7	6	19 (63.4%)
No fixed time	-	-	1	1 (3.3%)
Total	10	10	10	30 (100%)

Table 1:- Time spent on social media by the teachers

Table 1 shows that 63.4 per cent of teachers spent 2-3 hours on social media. These teachers shared that they regularly used social media for both personal communication and professional development.

33.3 per cent of teachers spent less than 2 hours on social media, these teachers had a fixed schedule for social media usage, and they made sure that their usage did not exceed 2 hours. They even ignored WhatsApp Messages and replied only to those texts which felt were worth replying to. Once they read the texts, they marked them as unread to avoid further communication.

One teacher (3.3 per cent) shared that she had no fixed time for social media usage, she said that her students were free to text her or share things with her after school hours, and she used social media to maintain communication with her parents and her relatives, chatting and replying to the texts of her connections took most of the time of this teacher. As a result, she had to keep on checking her smartphone.

B. Social media used by the teachers for teaching

Churcher, Downs, and Tewksbury (2014: 40) found in their study that social media like Facebook was effectively utilized by the teachers for engaging students in the learning process after school or college hours; many students who were hesitant to engage with teachers during the classroom lectures found it easy to express themselves on the Facebook posts of their teachers. Students were able to build a good rapport with their teachers, and those students who were excellent at written communication than verbal communication were able to express themselves without any hesitation. Chen and Bryer (2012: 89) found that social media like LinkedIn, WordPress, and Wikipedia were effectively used for merging formal and informal learning by rendering engaging channels through the various multimedia formats which facilitated connectivity and communication between the students and their fellow students, teachers and their

students through various multimedia platforms. Social media aided in the learning and connectivity of students with various online learning communities, the subject experts, and peers studying their subject across the world. Thus, teachers were asked about the social media that they used for teaching their students. Table 2. shows their responses:

Social Media Used by the Teachers for Teaching	Schools			Total
	GNPS	DPS	SPS	
YouTube and WhatsApp Messenger	10	5	7	22 (73.4%)
WhatsApp Messenger	-	4	-	4 (13.3%)
Google Classrooms, YouTube, WhatsApp Messenger	-	1	3	4 (13.3%)
Total	10	10	10	30 (100%)

Table 2:- Social media used by the teachers for teaching

Table 2 shows that all 30 teachers used social media for teaching. 73.4 per cent of teachers used YouTube and WhatsApp Messenger for teaching their students. Teachers shared that they used WhatsApp Messenger to send an important notice, updates regarding house tests or changes in house tests, lesson plans of science, mathematics, and social studies in PDF. The teachers also shared YouTube educational videos through WhatsApp Messenger. Lesson plans usually comprised fun facts associated with the topic and information about the topic, which was otherwise not possible for teachers to share in the classroom. The teachers used YouTube to access videos on subjects like chemistry, physics, social sciences, and biology. Teachers shared that YouTube videos were shown in the classrooms. WhatsApp Messenger was also used for creating groups for students and their subject teachers along with their class teachers. 13.3 per cent of teachers used WhatsApp Messenger for teaching their students, and another 13.3 per cent of teachers used Google Classrooms, YouTube, and WhatsApp Messenger. All the teachers used WhatsApp Messenger for immediate communication with the students and parents of the students. Teachers also used Google Classroom for sharing assignments, especially for science and mathematics subjects.

When the teachers in GNPS, DPS, and SPS were interviewed, they all admitted that the most significant change which COVID-19 pandemic brought was the transition from the four-walled concrete classrooms to the virtual classrooms. Zoom, Google Meet, and Microsoft Teams became popular social media among the teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic. Initially, when the online classes were announced, teachers had no option but to use Zoom for conducting online classes. However, there were serious concerns raised by the Indian government on the safety of Zoom. Jio Meet was launched right after people denied using Zoom, but teachers in all the three schools GNPS, DPS, and SPS revealed that they moved from Zoom to Google Meet. So, in all three school teachers first made use of Zoom and then Google Meet. Google Meet was very popular among the teachers in GNPS and SPS.

C. Gender Variations in Students’ Social Media Usage

Herring and Kapidzic (2015: 4) found that online self-presentation on social media is different for teenage boys and girls in terms of the content shared on their social media profiles – girls preferred sharing attractive and cute pictures whereas boys shared pictures which helped them assert their masculinity like those which referred to sexuality or alcohol. Girls were more concerned about their privacy, so many of them did not make their profiles and posts public. They preferred communicating with only those social media users they already know compared to the boys who made their profile and posts public for all. The boys shared fictitious information about themselves more often in comparison to the girls, and the text messages or comments of the boys reflected a belligerent tone and flirtatiousness; girls were more emotional and would support online connections more personally and give into favorable agreements over an issue shared by their connections on social media (Herring & Kapidzic, 2015). Similar findings were also reported by Siibak and Hernwall (2011), who found in their study that young boys and girls from the age group of 10-14 years constructed and reconstructed their online gender identities based on stereotype gender markers of masculinity and femininity. The girls in specific were found to be attention seekers by emphasizing their sexuality, like by pouting. The girls also manipulated their photos by editing them through photoshop or photo filters to gain more attention and positive comments from other friends.

Thus, the teachers of GNPS, DPS, and SPS were asked if their students’ social media usage varied with gender. Table 3. shows their responses:

Gender Variations in Students’ Social Media Usage	Schools			Total
	GNPS	DPS	SPS	
Equal social media usage by girls and boys with no variation	8	6	8	22 (73.3%)
Variation in social media usage of boys and girls	1	3	2	6 (20%)
Not aware	1	1	-	2 (6.7%)
Total	10	10	10	30 (100%)

Table 3:- Teachers on gender variations in students’ social media usage

Table 3. shows that according to 73.3 per cent of teachers, there was no variation in social media usage based on gender because girls and boys equally used social media and had access to modern gadgets in their homes. A teacher from GNPS said that the boys and girls were using social media in the similar fashion. According to her boys were also very expressive just like girls. When it came to Facebook, boys were as much conscious as girls and boys too appeared to be self-censoring their pictures by using filters.

Another teacher from DPS said that social media was more about imitation. She observed that boys and girls imitated each other. The trend among her students was to get clicked at fancy locations – it could be an upscale restaurant, a mall, a tourist destination like Malaysia, Singapore for this attracted them more friends. She said, *“From WhatsApp Dp to Facebook pages, children are far ahead of their times, I believe they very well know how to play in the game of social media. I don’t think there is any variation in the way they post, share things or comment on social media.”*

A teacher from SPS said that elder cousin brothers and sisters who get exposed to social media influence the behavior of the adolescents. She also shared that social media was negatively impacting friendships of adolescents. She said, *“With the social media friendships have taken shape of deceit and mischief and it is not limited to school – the moment child reaches home he or she has a gadget to connect or communicate with the school friend through social media....”*

20 per cent of teachers said that there was variation in the social media usage of boys and girls. These teachers said that girls used more emoticons and pictures than the boys who usually preferred plain text messages for communication with their teachers. A teacher from DPS said that girls in her class used more colorful emojis, GIFs, when they texted them, this was rare for boys. Girls wrote big text messages to their teachers whenever they had an academic query whereas boys wrote brief text message.

Some teachers felt that girls were more responsible than boys. A teacher from SPS said, *“Girls are more cautious as compared to boys. Boys are careless and they post things/comments/messages without thinking about the repercussions.”* Another teacher from GNPS said, *“Even though usage of girls and boys might be same, but girls are more disciplined. It takes less time to guide girls in the right direction, guiding boys is little difficult especially if they are adamant.”*

Only two teachers (6.7 per cent) shared that they were not aware of the social media usage of the boys and girls in their class to discern if there was any variation in the usage of social media in terms of the gender of the students.

Some teachers said that a few boys and girls have groups on social media like WhatsApp Messenger, and they do not use it constructively but destructively. A few teachers revealed that students plan all their mischievous activities with their peers on social media.

D. Teachers on Nuisance caused by the Social Media Usage of their students

The previous studies have confirmed that several problems accompany social media usage by teachers and students. Teachers complain about problems related to the privacy of the personal content which they share on social media as one of the important problems apart from privacy, lack of integrity of the students in terms of submissions or assignments shared through social media as significant

barriers for teacher-taught relationship and a major obstacle for effective teaching through social media (Carter, Foulger, & Ewbank, 2008; Moran, Seaman, & Tinti-Kane, 2011; Moran, Seaman, & Tinti-Kane, 2012; Seaman & Tinti-Kane, 2013). Eden, Heiman, and Olenik-Shemesh (2012) found that teachers observe cyberbullying as a common problem in schools.

Thus, teachers were asked if they experienced nuisance caused by the social media usage of their students.

Nuisance Caused by the Students' Social Media Usage	Schools			Total
	GNPS	DPS	SPS	
Experienced nuisance in the classrooms	4	7	10	21 (70%)
Have heard from colleagues about the nuisance caused by social media usage in the classrooms	3	3	-	6 (20%)
Did not experience any nuisance in the classrooms	3	-	-	3 (10%)
Total	10	10	10	30 (100%)

Table 4:- Teachers on the nuisance caused by the social media usage of their students

70 per cent of the teachers experienced nuisance caused by social media usage of the students in their classrooms. These teachers said that inappropriate use of social media by the students in the classrooms can negatively impact the teacher-taught relationships. Students were not allowed to carry smartphones in all the three schools. If the smartphones were allowed for rare cases, wherein the child was sick or living as a paying guest (PG) in the city, then also the teacher was required to take over the smartphone from the child during the school hours and return the smartphone to the child when school timings got over. Smartphones otherwise were confiscated if brought to school without any genuine reason backed by prior approval by the school principal. School wise, SPS and DPS had more teachers than GNPS who had experienced the nuisance caused by the social media usage in their classrooms.

20 per cent of teachers shared that they were very strict, and they did not face any nuisance but they did get to hear from their colleagues about the nuisance caused by social media usage in their classrooms. Teachers shared that there were a few cases of students who clicked pictures of their teachers, made funny memes and shared it in their WhatsApp Groups. Such students often got caught up when intelligent and dedicated students complain to the concerned teachers. Teachers said that it was very disheartening to deal with students who brought mobile phones to classrooms. A teacher from DPS said, *“Every teacher is a human being and it is not always easy to catch such students every time.”*

10 per cent of teachers said that they did not experience any nuisance in their classrooms. GNPS was the only school where three teachers shared during the interview that they did not experience any nuisance caused by social media in their classrooms (Table 4). A teacher from GNPS said, *“Social media usage is not always a nuisance specifically if the students know their limits....”* If the teachers were very strict, then the mischievous students did not dare to cross their limits in the classrooms.

In order to understand the impact of social media on teacher-taught relationships, the following section will emphasize the responses given by the teachers for the impact of social media on the behavior and academic performance of their students.

E. Impact of Social Media on Students' Behavior and Academic Performance

In their study, Eden, Heiman, and Olenik-Shemesh (2012) found that school teachers were getting cyberbullying complaints from their school students. Teachers themselves experienced cyberbullying. The female teachers and teachers of younger children were more aware and concerned about the problem of cyberbullying in comparison to male teachers. Teachers unequivocally stood for stringent policies and raising awareness on the prevention of cyberbullying because it harmed the academic performance and behavior of the students. They also encouraged parents of their students to think of coping strategies for combating cyberbullying.

Thus, the teachers of GNPS, DPS, and SPS were asked about the impact of social media on their students' behavior and academic performance.

Students of GNPS, DPS, and SPS were not allowed to use smartphones in their schools, but teachers were aware that their students had access to smartphones and laptops at their homes. All teachers admitted that social media positively impacted their students' emotional well-being and development, especially shy or introverted students. Most of these teachers said that social media, especially educational channels on YouTube, made students very aware and keen on learning from educational channels. Teachers in DPS said that their students collaborated on various extra-curricular activities through social media like inter-school competitions and science group projects assigned by the school teachers. Some teachers from SPS said that they had few students volunteering for NGOs on Facebook as fundraisers and environmental campaign awareness leaders. All teachers said that social media are great applications for engaging students and enabling students to think out of the box, but irrespective of that, the negative impact of social media cannot be denied. Thus, the GNPS, DPS, and SPS teachers were asked to explain what made them reflect on the negative impact that social media had on their students.

Table 5 shows their responses:

Negative Impact of Social Media	Schools			Total
	GNPS	DPS	SPS	
Negative impact on the studies and poor performance in academics	4	3	-	7 (23.3%)
Complaints of parents	4	5	3	12 (40%)
Poor behavior, Poor Language and Negative impact on the Studies	2	2	7	11 (36.7%)
Total	10	10	10	30 (100%)

Table 5:- Negative impact of social media on the students

Table 5. shows that 40 per cent of teachers received complaints from the parents of their students regarding their excessive social media usage. These teachers said that parents often complained that their children wasted time on social media. It was common for students to avoid their parents and not listen to them while using social media. Teachers said that some parents also complained of their children not eating food on time because of their time on smartphones and social media.

36.7 per cent of teachers said that social media usage by their students led to poor behavior, poor language, and adverse effect on their studies. Two teachers in SPS shared that they faced cyberbullying by students, and strict action was taken against those students. One of the two teachers of SPS said, *"I came to know that few non-serious students wrote something on the social media about my teaching, the post was later taken down by the students but I really felt hurt. Such things can distance students from their teachers...."* Another teacher of SPS also shared the problems of poor and cheap language proliferating through the social media and she said, *"I got complaint of some students maintaining fake accounts on the Facebook. Some students started posting cheap comments and forwarding inappropriate messages to other students with fake accounts which distracted students and their studies."*

A few teachers expressed that sometimes misunderstandings develop between their students and their peers, especially when the students form groups on social media, which leads to cyberbullying to the extent that the matter often reaches them, and they were required to take strict action against the violators.

A teacher of SPS explained why misbehavior in the form of cyberbullying is common on the social media, she said, *"Such things occur because students comment by imitating their peer group on social media, they do not know the meaning of what they are saying and they do not know what it would lead to, they take such things as fun but on the contrary such issues can actually disturb their peace of mind."*

A teacher of DPS shared that WhatsApp Messenger groups can be a problem for the students. She said, *"Once when we formed a WhatsApp Broadcast Group students had access to numbers of other students and they started creating problems for each other. We then took strict action against such students and students were guided not to get into such things."*

23.3 per cent of teachers said that excessive social media usage led to a negative effect on the studies of their students. They said that their students' academic performance got poor, especially when social media was not used under parental supervision. According to these teachers, students often lied to their parents that they used social media like YouTube for homework, and parents complained to the teachers during the parent-teacher meetings (PTM's). So, these teachers said that they do not give homework to their students that would require excessive usage of Internet and social media. The responses by the teachers also revealed that the student's academic performance did not determine their social media usage or the problems faced by the students on social media. Interviews of the students from all the three schools also corroborated what teachers shared about their students, as many students who were intelligent and good in academics shared that they considered social media an inseparable aspect of their lives. The problems faced by the use of social media were quite similar for all the students, irrespective of their gender and performance in academics. Though some teachers felt strictness was not the solution, most of the teachers felt that only love and care could bring about a positive change in the students' behavior, and proper guidance can help limit the social media usage of the students. Teachers felt that the dependence on social media is the biggest drawback, and students have got so much used to receiving the educational information or school updates to the extent that if the updates are sent via notice board, students will not bother to pay attention to the notice board. A teacher from DPS said, *"I passed information to one student and asked her to tell other students to see the notice board, the girl relayed the information to students but some forgot to see the notice board and started giving lame excuses that they didn't get information in written."* Teachers said that intelligent and responsible students realize after a particular time that if they become excessive social media users, that would undoubtedly impact their academics.

Teachers of all the three schools GNPS, DPS, and SPS, attributed the negative impact of social media on the lives of the adolescent students to the fact that most of the families were nuclear families and both the parents were working. A teacher from DPS said, *"Earlier joint families were there, so the children were taken well care of, but now mostly nuclear families exist and parents are working, so technology has seeped into the lives of the children."* She continued and said, *"Naturally, if the child is alone at home, then he or she is going to rely on a smartphone or laptop to keep himself or herself busy."* Another teacher of DPS, in agreement with her, said, *"In cases where parents are working it is not wrong to leave the child with the smartphone but it is equally important for working parents to guide their children about*

being safe on social media and limit their social media usage.”

Some teachers felt that social media could positively or negatively impact the students’ academics and teacher-taught relationships depending on how it was used. A teacher from DPS said, *“If we direct students in the right way and guide them about appropriately utilizing social media then it will definitely make things more interesting to learn and do with.”*

Another teacher of DPS asserted that students should be motivated to use social media only for educational purposes, *“The focus of parents and teachers should be on motivating the students to use social media only for study purpose and making sure that child stays away from unwanted content which has got nothing to do with their studies.”*

F. Coping Mechanisms of the teachers for their Students’ Social Media Problems

Studies have substantiated that even though teachers were aware of the face-to-face bullying problem in their school, very few teachers were aware of problems like cyberbullying, which took place outside their school premises. Teachers played a very significant role in coping with cyberbullying, considering that cyberbullying harmed the studies and concentration of the students (Willard, 2007; Mason & Rennie, 2008). Teachers were required to intervene in the classroom by addressing the problems of their students who were victims by collaborating with the parents to control the menace and keep a check on the students who were bullies. Teachers also played a significant role in anti-cyberbullying programs through prompt management of the emotions by redressing the grievances of their victim students through coherent care and reaction. Teachers could motivate the victim students to give up fear by being bold enough in reporting cyberbullying (Migliore, 2003; Willard, 2005; Epstein & Kazmierczak, 2007). Thus, it was important to ask the teachers about their coping mechanisms for problems stimulated by their students’ excessive social media usage. Table 6. shows their responses:

Coping Mechanisms	Schools			Total
	GNPS	DPS	SPS	
Counseling and Guidance	5	8	2	15 (50%)
Inform Principal, Headmistress or Coordinator of School	3	1	2	6 (20%)
Advise the parents to keep a check apart from counseling students	2	1	6	9 (30%)
Total	10	10	10	30 (100%)

Table 6:- Teachers’ coping mechanisms for their students’ social media problems

Table 6 shows that 50 per cent of teachers used counseling and guidance as coping mechanism. These teachers personally counseled students and helped them to

make better use of social media. These teachers said that they conducted special sessions for counseling and guiding students to eliminate the problems stimulated by their students’ excessive social media usage. 30 per cent of teachers advised the parents of their students to keep a check on the social media usage apart from counseling their students. 20 per cent of teachers said that they reported the principal, headmistress, or coordinator of their respective schools because they felt that stern action taken against the students created a fear in the mind of the students, which prevented them from using social media in the classrooms. It also avoided social media problems like cyberbullying outside the school premises.

In SPS, most of the teachers, apart from counseling their students, advised the parents of the students to keep a check on their social media usage, whereas most of the teachers of GNPS and DPS preferred counseling and guiding their students for the problems caused by the social media usage.

In DPS, there were different coordinators for different class levels: there were four separate coordinators for Classes up to V, Classes to VIII, Classes to X, and Classes to XII. These coordinators passed on the information/directions to other teachers, and then a faculty meeting took place in which issues about student welfare were discussed, the issued directions were then passed on to the students. Cyber talks were also conducted in DPS.

Teachers of all the three schools GNPS, DPS, and SPS, felt that parents should check the online and offline activities of their children as children spend time with them at home after school hours. Teachers expressed that even though for working parents it might not be possible for the parents to check on the smartphone of their children, but parents should limit the time hours their children spent on social media – parents should spend some more time with their children to know about their lives and how they are doing in personal as well as academic lives. A teacher from SPS said that she parents of her student to take away his smartphone and give it to him as a reward only when he does well in the classroom. She also said that she guided her students about misuse/hacking of information shared on social media, viruses spread by hackers. She often advised parents to avoid giving smartphone to their children for long hours and restrict the social media usage of their children. Another teacher of SPS said, *“I advise parents to secure the WiFi with a password which is known only to them so that children use Internet and social media under their supervision but very few parents pay heed, many don't bother at all.”*

When it came to life-threatening and unsafe games like Blue Whale Challenge, teachers of all three schools were very concerned. They expressed unequivocally that the proliferation of games like Blue Whale Challenge proves that young adolescents were prone to get misguided or directed towards wrong ideas, which influenced them or seemed challenging. A teacher from DPS said, *“We all know that Blue Whale Challenge not only gave challenges to the adolescents but it also scared them and forced them to take*

up that Challenge, this also proves that adolescents have sensitive minds and they can easily get scared to do wrong or tolerate wrong." Another teacher of GNPS said, "Such kind of involvement of students is because we as parents allow them to be more with social media than with us."

Teachers of all the three schools, GNPS, DPS, and SPS, felt that sensitization on issues pertaining to cyber-crime should not be merely for the students, but their parents as well need to be sensitized about such issues. They said that they did sensitize parents during parent-teacher meetings (PTMs). A teacher from DPS said, "Our school keeps sensitizing students as well as parents in PTMs and orientation programs for healthy use of social media." A teacher from GNPS said, "Students were informed about the harmful effects of technology in regular class assemblies. Parents were also advised to keep a check on their children. There is a school counselor who takes care of such issues. Teachers also give hundred percent when it comes to guiding the students."

A school coordinator teaching at SPS said, "Our Principal, teachers and school counselor take extra care in such issues. During Blue Whale Challenge thing, parents were informed by the principal and directions were given to the parents to ensure the safety of their child."

A teacher from SPS shared that she used performing arts to make her students understand the harm that is accompanied by excessive and unbridled social media usage. She said, "I conducted a class assembly for Class IX students in which a play based on social media was shown to the students. The emphasis was laid on the advantages and disadvantages of the social media with all scenes carrying relevant information for a child to understand the repercussions of using the social media in a negative way and positive way."

In all three schools, the school counselor sensitized the students. DPS and SPS took extreme care on such issues. A school coordinator teaching at DPS said, "Not only our teachers and counselors took excessive care, but under the supervision and support of the Principal Madam, we even conducted a talk through which experts on cyber-crime created awareness." Another teacher of SPS said, "In 2017 our school conducted a Shivalik Declamation Contest: 'WhatsApp a life line/a life cut' and students came up with brilliant ideas. The main motive behind conducting this contest was to sensitize students about the positives and negatives of WhatsApp. We keep on organizing such activities."

Thus, when it came to excessive social media usage, then the teachers in all the three schools, especially SPS, believed that parents must keep a check on the amount of time which their child spends on social media because, at home, only parents can efficiently monitor the activities of their child on the social media. All the teachers strongly felt that students should know 'how, when, why, and where' of using social media.

Smartphones and social media could lead to a dependency that becomes an inseparable aspect of user's life and existence (Turkle, 2012). Thus, the teachers' dependency on social media can be studied by understanding the extent to which they considered social media an inseparable aspect of their lives.

IV. CONCLUSION

The findings highlighted that the teachers were optimistic about the application of social media usage for teaching. Teachers effectively used social media, with many of them regularly using social media to teach their students. WhatsApp Messenger was the most preferred social media by the teachers for communicating with their students, and they even made use of YouTube to share insightful educational videos with their students. However, the teachers were optimistic about the social media usage of their students. Teachers did not deny the negative impacts of social media on their students' behavior, language, and academic performance. Teachers shared during the interviews that even though their students were making positive use of social media for their studies, but at the same time, some students had become notorious, and some others lost their original thinking or creativity. Some other students who mindlessly imitated their friends on social media could not concentrate on their studies.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Carter, H. L., Foulger, T. S., & Ewbank, A. D. (2008). Have you googled your teacher lately? *Teachers' use of social networking sites. Phi Delta Kappan*, 89(9), 681-685.
- [2]. Casey, G., & Evans, T. (2011). Designing for learning: Online social networks as a classroom environment. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 12(7), 1-26.
- [3]. Chen, B., & Bryer, T. (2012). Investigating instructional strategies for using social media in formal and informal learning. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 13(1), 87-104.
- [4]. Churcher, K. M. A., Downs, E., & Tewksbury, D. (2014). "Friending" Vygotsky: A social constructivist pedagogy of knowledge building through classroom social media use. *The Journal of Effective Teaching*, 14(1), 33-50.
- [5]. Domizi, D. P. (2013). Microblogging to foster connections and community in a weekly graduate seminar course. *TechTrends*, 57(1), 43-51
- [6]. Eden, S., Heiman, T., & Olenik-Shemesh, D. (2012). Teachers' perceptions, beliefs and concerns about cyberbullying. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 44(6), 1036-1052.
- [7]. Epstein, A., & Kazmierczak, J. (2007). Cyber bullying: what teachers, social workers, and administrators should know. *Illinois Child Welfare*, 3, 41-51.
- [8]. Fewkes, A. M. & McCabe, M. (2012). Facebook: Learning Tool or Distraction? *Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education*, 28(3), 92-98.

- [9]. Graham, M. (2014). Social media as a tool for increased student participation and engagement outside the classroom in higher education. *Journal of Perspectives in Applied Academic Practice*, 2(3), 16-24.
- [10]. Herring, S. C., & Kapidzic, S. (2015). Teens, gender, and self-presentation in social media. *International Encyclopedia of Social and Behavioral sciences*, 2, 1-16.
- [11]. Junco, R., Heiberger, G. & Loken, E. (2011). The effect of Twitter on college Student engagement and grades. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 27, 119-132.
- [12]. June, S., Yaacob, A. & Kheng, Y. K. (2014). Assessing the Use of YouTube Videos and Interactive Activities as a Critical Thinking Stimulator for Tertiary Students: An Action Research. *International Education Studies*, 7(8), 56-67.
- [13]. Krutka, D., & Milton, M. K. (2013). The Enlightenment Meets Twitter: Using Social Media In The Social Studies Classroom. *Ohio Social Studies Review*, 50(2), 22-29.
- [14]. Lee, S. (2009). Online Communication and Adolescent Social Ties: Who benefits more from Internet use? *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 14(3), 509-531.
- [15]. Mander, J., Kavanagh, D., & Buckle, C. (2019). Global Web Index's Flagship Report on The Latest Trends in Social Media. *Social*. Retrieved from: <https://www.gwi.com/reports/social-2019>
- [16]. Mason, R., & Rennie, F. (2008). *The E-Learning Handbook: Social Networking for Higher Education*. London: Routledge.
- [17]. Migliore, E. (2003). Eliminate bullying in your classroom. *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 38(3), 172-176.
- [18]. Moran, M., Seaman, J., & Tinti-Kane, H. (2011). *Teaching, Learning, and Sharing: How Today's Higher Education Faculty Use Social Media*. Pearson Learning Solutions and Babson Survey Research Group. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED535130.pdf>
- [19]. Moran, M., Seaman, J., & Tinti-Kane, H. (2012). *Blogs, wikis, podcasts and Facebook: How today's higher education faculty use social media*. Pearson Learning Solutions and Babson Survey Research Group. Retrieved from: https://www.bayviewanalytics.com/reports/blogswikis_podcasts.pdf
- [20]. Nie, N. H., & Erbring, L. (2002). Internet and Society: A Preliminary Report. *IT & society*, 1(1), 275-283. Retrieved from <http://csriu.org/cyberbully/docs/cbcteducator.pdf>
- [21]. Seaman, J., & Tinti-Kane, H. (2013). *Social media for teaching and learning*. Pearson Learning Solutions and Babson Survey Research Group. Retrieved from: <https://www.bayviewanalytics.com/reports/social-media-for-teaching-and-learning-2013-report.pdf>
- [22]. Sherer, P., & Shea, T. (2011). Using Online Video to Support Student Learning and Engagement. *College Teaching*, 59(2), 56-59.
- [23]. Siibak, A., & Hernwall, P. (2011). 'Looking like my favourite Barbie'-Online Gender Construction of Tween Girls in Estonia and in Sweden. *Studies of Transition States and Societies*, 3(2), 57-68.
- [24]. Turkle, S. (2012). *Alone Together: Why We Expect More from Technology and Less From Each Other*. New York: Basic Books. [Paperback book was published in 2012]
- [25]. Willard, N.E. (2005). *An educator's guide to cyber bullying and cyberthreats: responding to the challenge of online social aggression, threats, and distress*. Center for Safe and Responsible Internet Use (CSRIU). Retrieved from <http://www.cyberbully.org/docs/cbcteducator.pdf>
- [26]. Willard, N.E. (2007). Educators' guide to cyberbullying and Cyberthreats. Retrieved from: <http://csriu.org/cyberbully/docs/cbcteducator.pdf>